

A Decade of Consumer Behavior Research in Indonesia: Cultural, Technological, and Economic Influences

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Abstract

This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of consumer behavior trends in Indonesia through a literature review of various studies conducted from 2015 to 2024. Using a systematic method to review and synthesize journal articles, this study explores how cultural, social, economic, and technological factors influence consumer purchasing decisions in Indonesia. Key findings suggest that rich socio-cultural values and increasing technology penetration have significantly changed the way Indonesian consumers interact with the market. The review also highlights changes in shopping behavior driven by the growth of e-commerce and social media, as well as shifts in values and expectations among the younger generation. The study identifies several important gaps in the literature, including the lack of longitudinal studies, the paucity of research in non-urban areas, and the need for deeper analysis of the interaction between local cultural values and digital technology adoption. This study provides new insights into how cultural, technological, and economic changes interrelate with consumer behavior in Indonesia. The implications of the study's findings emphasize the importance of data-driven and adaptive marketing strategies to meet the needs of dynamic Indonesian consumers. Further studies are needed to address these gaps in order to provide a more holistic understanding of consumer behavior.

Keywords: *Consumer Behavior, Indonesia, E-commerce, Cultural Values, Millennial Generation, Literature Review.*

Suggested citation: Rialisnawati, Rahmatunnisya, H., Dopo, M.R., Kalsum, N., & Husnan, L.H. (2024). A Decade of Consumer Behavior Research in Indonesia: Cultural, Technological, and Economic Influences. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 1(3), 33-42. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2024.1(3).02

Introduction

Consumer behavior is a field of study that continues to evolve as social, cultural, and technological dynamics influence the way consumers interact with products and services around the world (Lesmana, 2023; Murin et al., 2015). In Indonesia, as a country with a large and heterogeneous population, the study of consumer behavior is becoming increasingly relevant to understand the diverse preferences, habits, and consumption patterns across various segments of society (Rochdiani, 2023). Indonesia, with its growing economy and rapidly growing middle class, presents a unique context for consumer behavior researchers, given the complexity of local cultures, the influence of globalization, and rapid lifestyle shifts.

In recent decades, increased access to technology and digitalization have influenced the way Indonesian consumers behave. E-commerce platforms, social media, and digital marketing are now key elements in consumer interactions with products and services (Long et al., 2024; Rana et al., 2024). Studies on digital consumer behavior in Indonesia have increased rapidly along with the increasing use of technology among consumers, especially in big cities. In addition, global trends such as environmental awareness and green consumption are starting to influence Indonesian consumer behavior, although it is still in its early stages compared to developed countries.

However, consumer behavior in Indonesia is not only influenced by economic and technological factors, but also by strong traditional and social values. Factors such as culture, religion, and local ethics often influence consumer purchasing decisions and loyalty to certain brands (Agarwal & Dubey, 2024; Katrandjiev, 2011). Therefore, research on consumer behavior in Indonesia is becoming increasingly important to understand how consumers balance modernity with strong cultural identities in choosing products and services.

Research on consumer behavior trends in Indonesia covers a wide range of aspects, such as preferences for local versus global products, purchasing decisions in a digital context, and changes in consumption behavior during crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic. However, while interest in this topic continues to grow, there are still gaps in the literature on certain aspects of consumer behavior, such as the impact of the digital economy outside major cities, changes in ethical consumption patterns, and the influence of socio-economic changes on consumption behavior.

Along with the development of the times, consumer behavior in Indonesia cannot be separated from three main factors: culture, technology, and economy. Culture plays an important role in shaping consumer preferences, especially in a country with diversity like Indonesia. Local values, traditions, and social norms often influence consumer purchasing decisions, creating unique dynamics in the market.

Technological advancements, especially in the last decade, have brought about significant changes. The adoption of e-commerce and social media has not only facilitated product accessibility but also created new patterns of interaction between consumers and brands. Technology has become a key enabler for consumers to make purchases faster and more efficiently, while online reviews and algorithm-based recommendations have further strengthened consumer trust.

From an economic perspective, the growth of the middle class in Indonesia has increased people's purchasing power. In addition, the global economic crisis, including the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, has presented new challenges that have affected consumption patterns. Consumers are now more careful in spending their money, with a greater focus on value, quality, and sustainability.

This study aims to reveal how these three elements interact and shape consumer behavior in Indonesia. Thus, this study not only provides academic insight but also practical implications for business actors in designing more effective and relevant strategies. As well as to review and present a comprehensive literature review on research trends on consumer behavior in Indonesia. By reviewing various previous studies, it is hoped that this study can identify the main patterns, key issues faced by researchers, and reveal gaps that need to be answered by future research. In addition, this literature review also seeks to provide insight for practitioners and academics in understanding the complexity of consumer behavior in Indonesia which is experiencing rapid changes, both in terms of technology, culture, and social aspects.

Method

To analyze consumer behavior trends in Indonesia, this study uses a bibliometric method facilitated by the VOSviewer application. This technique allows the identification of keywords, relationships

between topics, and distribution of research in the field of consumer behavior. This bibliometric analysis focuses on three main elements: culture, technology, and economy.

The steps taken include:

1. Data Collection: Articles were taken from Google Scholar indexed journals relevant to the topic of consumer behavior in the period 2015–2024.
2. Bibliometric Analysis: Identify frequently occurring keywords, such as “e-commerce,” “consumer trust,” “social media,” “pandemic,” and “cultural values.” This data is then mapped to see the relationships between themes.
3. Thematic Synthesis: Articles are analyzed qualitatively to explore trends within each key category. Focus is given on how these three factors influence consumer behavior in Indonesia.

The results of this analysis provide in-depth insights into research trends as well as gaps that need to be addressed in future studies.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1. Graph Number of Publications on the Topic of "Consumer Behavior" from 2015 to 2024

The graph above (Figure 1) shows the trend in the number of publications related to consumer behavior from 2015 to 2024. The horizontal axis shows the time span covering 2015 to 2024, with each dot representing the number of publications published per year. Meanwhile, the vertical axis depicts the total number of publications, ranging from 100,000 to 300,000 publications. From 2015 to 2024, the number of publications has increased steadily, starting from 110,000 publications in 2015 to 230,000 publications in 2024. This shows the increasing interest in research in the field of consumer behavior during this period.

From 2015 to 2022, there is a consistent upward trend in the number of publications related to consumer behavior. In 2015, the number of publications was recorded at around 100,000, and gradually increased almost two-fold to exceed 250,000 publications in 2022. This peak in 2022 likely reflects the very high interest in the topic of consumer behavior, which could have been triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic. The major changes in consumer behavior during the pandemic appear to have driven a lot of new research in this area.

During the period from 2015 to 2022, the number of publications related to consumer behavior has increased significantly. In 2015, the number of publications was around 100,000 and continued to almost double to reach more than 250,000 in 2022. The peak number of publications occurred in 2022, which was most likely influenced by the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic triggered drastic changes in consumer behavior, which in turn increased researchers' interest in studying this phenomenon in more depth, resulting in more publications in the field.

Between 2015 and 2022, there was a significant increase in the number of publications discussing consumer behavior. In 2015, the number of publications was around 100,000, and it continued to almost double to exceed 250,000 in 2022. The peak number of publications occurred in 2022, which was likely influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic, where major changes in consumer behavior drove increased research interest. This phenomenon reflects how shifts in global consumption patterns became a major concern for researchers during the period.

Between 2015 and 2022, the number of publications on consumer behavior has increased significantly. Starting from around 100,000 publications in 2015, this number has almost doubled to more than 250,000 in 2022. The peak of publications in 2022 is thought to have been triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has brought about major changes in consumer behavior worldwide. This surge in research shows how changes in consumption patterns during the pandemic have become a major concern in academic and scientific studies.

Between 2015 and 2022, the number of publications related to consumer behavior has increased significantly. In early 2015, the number of publications was around 100,000, but gradually increased almost twofold to exceed 250,000 in 2022. This highest peak occurred in 2022, which was most likely influenced by the COVID-19 pandemic, which resulted in major changes in consumer behavior. This reflects the increasing interest of researchers in studying changes in consumption patterns that emerged during the pandemic, thus driving a significant growth in the number of publications.

Figure 2. Research Relationship Network Map on Consumer Behavior in Indonesia

Network map that maps the relationship of keywords or terms related to "consumer behavior". This image is generated from the analysis of co-occurrence or the simultaneous occurrence of keywords from various articles or scientific publications. Conceptual connectedness in consumer behavior illustrates how various aspects related to this behavior are interconnected and influence each other (Gunawan Aji et al., 2023). This figure highlights that the concept of consumer behavior does not stand alone, but is closely connected to several other important elements. One of them is the COVID-19 pandemic, which has significantly affected consumer behavior, especially in increasing online shopping (e-commerce) and reshaping risk perceptions and purchasing preferences (Mardiani et al., 2020). In addition, brands play a central role in how consumers interact, especially through social media, which influences consumer engagement and their relationship with a particular brand (Rahman et al., 2024; Safira & Aryansyah, 2023). Another aspect that is no less important is trust, where many studies show that the level of consumer trust in a product or brand has a direct impact on purchasing decisions and consumer loyalty to the brand (Esa Sekar Hastari et al., 2023; Hantika et al., 2023). This interconnectedness shows the complexity of consumer behavior, which is influenced by various external and internal factors in the decision-making process.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on consumer behavior (Abdullah & Suliyanthini, 2021; Rohmah, 2020), as reflected by the strong correlation between the keywords "consumer behavior" and "covid" in the study. During the pandemic, many consumers shifted to online shopping, which raised new challenges regarding trust in e-commerce platforms and concerns about the safety of the products and services offered (Rafanda et al., 2024). The increase in online shopping is also accompanied by the emergence of perceived risks, especially in terms of hygiene and product quality, which are the main concerns of consumers during the pandemic (Safitri et al., 2022). In addition, consumers' perceptions of the health risks posed by the pandemic have drastically changed their shopping patterns, with a greater preference for products that are considered safe and reliable (Sahira & Fauziyah, 2021). This transformation shows that the pandemic has not only affected the way consumers purchase products, but also changed the key factors that influence their purchasing decisions, such as safety, trust, and perceived risk.

Trust, loyalty and consumer engagement are three important elements that are interrelated in building long-term relationships between consumers and brands (Saputri M et al., 2023; Sitaniapessy et al., 2022). Consumer trust in a brand or product plays a key role in the decision-making process, especially in digital marketing where interactions occur quickly and often indirectly (Ahdiany, 2021). Consumers who trust a brand tend to be more willing to make purchases and use the services offered. This trust is the foundation for building consumer loyalty, which is a long-term commitment to continue choosing and using the brand.

On the other hand, consumer engagement plays an important role in strengthening the relationship between consumers and brands (Bakhtiar & Jayanto, 2015). This engagement includes the active participation of consumers in interactions with brands, whether through social media, product reviews, or direct communication on digital platforms. In the digital ecosystem, consumer feedback and interactions can spread quickly, so positive engagement has the potential to increase trust and loyalty. Therefore, a successful marketing strategy must be able to manage and maximize consumer engagement to strengthen emotional connections and trust in the brand, which ultimately results in ongoing loyalty.

During times of crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic, market behavior changes significantly, as reflected by the strong relationship between keywords such as crisis, pandemic, and consumer buying behavior. Many studies have highlighted how crisis situations affect consumer decision-making. One of the main impacts is the increased risk perception of consumers, which directly

affects the way they shop. Consumers tend to be more careful in choosing products, with a greater focus on safety and reliability.

In addition, the crisis also triggered a major shift towards online shopping, as consumers sought safer and more convenient ways to shop amidst uncertainty. Product preferences also changed, with increased demand for essential goods, health products, and items that support stay-at-home activities. Research during this period focused heavily on how consumers adapted their behavior, both in terms of product preferences and purchasing channels, to address the challenges posed by the crisis.

Consumer decision making is a complex process involving various factors, as seen from nodes such as product, consumer choice, and consumer resistance (Hidayat, 2017). Consumer choice refers to how consumers choose products or services based on a number of factors, such as product quality, price, brand trust, and recommendations from people around them. These choices are often influenced by previous experiences, specific needs, and perceptions of the value offered by the product.

On the other hand, consumer resistance describes a situation where consumers actively refuse to buy or follow a particular market trend. This resistance can be caused by several reasons, such as the price being considered too high, ethical concerns about the company's business practices, or the perception of excessive risks to the product, such as health or safety. In some cases, consumers also reject products because they do not match their personal values or preferences. Studies on consumer decision making often examine how these two aspects—choice and resistance—interact in market dynamics.

This visualization divides consumer behavior keywords into different thematic groups based on color, each reflecting a specific research area. The general behavior group (purple) highlights broad consumer behavior studies, including factors that influence decision-making. The crisis and COVID-19 group (green/blue) focuses on changes in consumer behavior during times of crisis, specifically the pandemic, which has led to increased online shopping and risk perception. The digital marketing and social media group (red) illustrates how brands' interactions with consumers via social media influence engagement and purchase decisions. Finally, the product and consumer choice group (brown) examines how consumers make product decisions, as well as the factors that influence product preferences, including brand loyalty and trust.

This visualization shows that consumer behavior is a highly complex topic influenced by a variety of factors, from global crises to digital marketing trends. Research in this area has been rapidly adapting to changes, such as the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, the rise in online shopping, the role of social media, and the importance of building consumer trust and loyalty in the digital age. Overall, this visualization illustrates how these factors interplay in the study of consumer behavior and highlights how research continues to evolve to adapt to changing dynamics in the global marketplace. This shows that consumer behavior is not only influenced by individual needs and preferences, but also by the broader context, such as crisis conditions and technology.

Cultural factors in Indonesia play a significant role in shaping people's consumption patterns. Indonesian consumers tend to maintain traditional and religious values in making purchasing decisions. Products that are considered in line with cultural values, such as halal food or products based on local wisdom, receive more attention from consumers.

In addition, in the context of traditional and religious celebrations, consumption increases significantly. For example, during moments such as Ramadan and Eid al-Fitr, consumers show a strong preference for certain products that have symbolic value in their culture. A study by Rochdiani (2023) confirmed that Indonesian consumers often prefer local products because they have an emotional attachment to their culture.

The younger generation in Indonesia, especially millennials and Gen Z, are showing a significant shift in preferences and consumption patterns. They are more open to technology and tend to seek practical and modern shopping experiences, such as through e-commerce and social media. This generation is also showing a higher awareness of sustainability and ethical issues.

Studies show that this generation tends to choose brands that have sustainability and social responsibility values. They are more attracted to eco-friendly products or companies that support social initiatives. This trend is also seen in their use of social media, where product reviews, influencer promotions, and brand campaigns play a significant role in influencing their purchasing decisions.

This change reflects a unique value shift in the younger generation, which positions them as one of the main drivers of market transformation in Indonesia. For companies, understanding the preferences of the younger generation is key to designing more relevant and effective marketing strategies.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the literature review, it can be concluded that consumer behavior in Indonesia in purchasing behavior is influenced by various interrelated factors, including culture, economy, technology, and generational changes. Cultural factors remain a dominant influence, where traditional values, religion, and social norms play an important role in purchasing decisions. Preferences for local and halal products show how local cultural values continue to influence Indonesian consumers, even in a modern context.

Younger generations, especially millennials and Gen Z, are showing a significant shift in consumption patterns. They are more likely to adopt digital technologies such as e-commerce and social media, and are more sensitive to sustainability and ethical issues. These changes are driving increased demand for eco-friendly products and socially responsible brands.

The interaction between culture, technology and economy is also evident. For example, the younger generation maintains cultural values such as consuming halal products, but uses digital platforms for easy access. From an economic perspective, the growth of the middle class and the impact of global crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic influence consumption priorities.

Consumers are increasingly selective in choosing products, with a focus on value, quality and sustainability.

Research Gap

This study also identified several gaps that require further attention, including:

1. **Lack of Longitudinal Data:** In-depth studies based on longitudinal data are needed to track changes in consumer behavior over the long term.
2. **Lack of Studies on the Influence of External Factors:** Research on the impact of government policies, global economic conditions, and international crises on consumer behavior is still limited.
3. **Lack of Focus on Consumers in Non-Urban Areas:** Most of the studies focus on big cities, while consumer behavior in rural areas has not been explored much.
4. **Cultural Influence on Digital Behavior:** Further research is needed to understand how local cultural values influence the adoption of digital technologies, such as online shopping.

5. Sustainable and Ethical Consumption Behavior: Studies on sustainable and ethical consumption in Indonesia are still in their early stages and require further exploration.

Implications

This research has important implications both practically and academically. From a practical perspective, the results of this study emphasize that companies need to develop marketing strategies that are data-driven and able to adapt to changing market dynamics. The penetration of e-commerce and social media, for example, requires a more personalized and interactive marketing approach to reach younger generations who are more sensitive to sustainability and ethical values.

In addition, a deep understanding of local cultural values can help companies create products and campaigns that are more relevant to Indonesian consumers. By paying attention to the differences in preferences between urban and rural areas, companies can also tap into untapped market opportunities.

From an academic perspective, this study opens up opportunities for further, more integrative and longitudinal studies. Further research is expected to explore more deeply the interaction between culture, technology, and economy, as well as the impact of external factors such as government policies or the global economic crisis on consumer behavior. This study also emphasizes the importance of expanding the scope of research to non-urban areas to provide a more comprehensive picture of Indonesian consumer behavior as a whole.

By addressing these gaps, future research can provide more holistic insights and help businesses and policy makers design more effective and sustainable solutions.

References

- Abdullah, C., & Suliyanthini, D. (2021). Perubahan Perilaku Konsumen di Masa Pandemi Covid-19. *Equilibrium: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 9, 18–24. <https://doi.org/10.26618/equilibrium.v9i1.4316>
- Agarwal, S., & Dubey, R. S. (2024). a Bibliometric and Thematic Review of Green Marketing and Green Consumer Behavior Research From 2000 To 2022. *Serbian Journal of Management*, 19(1), 51–70. <https://doi.org/10.5937/sjm19-45515>
- Ahdiany, D. F. (2021). Pengaruh E-Wom Dan Kesadaran Merek Terhadap Minat Beli Konsumen Dengan Citra Merek Sebagai Variabel Mediasi. *National Conference on Accounting & Finance*, 3(2003), 31–41. <https://doi.org/10.20885/ncaf.vol3.art3>
- Bakhtiar, A., & Jayanto, D. (2015). Analisis Elemen-Elemen Brand Equity Pada Produk Kartu Seluler Prabayar Simpati, Im3, Dan Xl Di Kalangan Mahasiswa S1 Universitas Diponegoro. *J@Ti Undip : Jurnal Teknik Industri*, 10(3), 155–162. <https://doi.org/10.12777/jati.10.3.155-162>
- Esa Sekar Hastari, Corry Yohana, & Arvinta Monoarfa, T. (2023). Pengaruh Kepercayaan Merek dan Kualitas Produk terhadap Loyalitas Konsumen melalui Kepuasan Konsumen sebagai Variabel Mediasi (Studi Kasus pada Brand Skincare Lokal). *Jurnal Bisnis, Manajemen, Dan Keuangan*, 3(3), 785–799. <https://doi.org/10.21009/jbmk.0303.13>
- Gunawan Aji, Natalia Casha, Siti Fatimah, & Allisa Qotrunnada Munawaroh. (2023). Pengaruh Budaya Terhadap Penerapan Strategi Pemasaran Internasional. *Jurnal Ekonomi, Manajemen Pariwisata Dan Perhotelan*, 2(2), 159–169. <https://doi.org/10.55606/jempper.v2i2.1427>
- Hantika, S., Farida, N., & Widiartanto, W. (2023). Pengaruh Kesadaran Merek dan Kepercayaan Merek terhadap Loyalitas Konsumen melalui Pembelian Ulang (Studi pada Konsumen Produk

- Merek Wardah di Kota Semarang). *Jurnal Ilmu Administrasi Bisnis*, 12(1), 175–183. <https://doi.org/10.14710/jiab.2023.37268>
- Hidayat, R. (2017). Faktor-Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Consumer Decision Making Process (Studi Kasus Rumah Makan Bebek Sinjai Madura). *Jiems (Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management Systems)*, 9(2), 77–95. <https://doi.org/10.30813/jiems.v9i2.40>
- Katrandjiev, H. (2011). Typology of consumer behavior in times of economic crisis: A segmentation study from Bulgaria. *Marketing*, 42(3), 161–170. <https://doi.org/10.5937/markt1103161k>
- Lesmana, T. (2023). Analisis Perilaku Konsumen Generasi Milenial Dalam Berbelanja Online. *Jurnal EBI*, 5(2), 46–56. <https://doi.org/10.52061/ebi.v5i2.175>
- Long, J., Zaidin, N., & Mai, X. (2024). Social media influencer streamers and live-streaming shopping: examining consumer behavioral intention through the lens of the theory of planned behavior. *Future Business Journal*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-024-00370-0>
- Mardiani, E., Rahmansyah, N., & Al Rizky, F. (2020). Perilaku Konsumen Terhadap E-Commerce Disaat Pandemi Covid 19 di Shop And Travel. *Informatik: Jurnal Ilmu Komputer*, 16(3), 212. <https://doi.org/10.52958/iftk.v16i3.2264>
- Murin, I., Marková, I., Zelený, J., & Jačud'ová, J. (2015). Green Marketing as a Tool Influencing Consumers' Behavior: Slovak Case Study of Regional Mark Preference. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 34(15), 260–267. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671\(15\)01628-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2212-5671(15)01628-7)
- Rafanda, S., Kurniawati, F., & Awali, H. (2024). Pengaruh Penggunaan Platform E- Commerce Terhadap Kinerja Penjualan Toko Offline Muda Mudi di Era Digital. *Jurnal Sabmiyya*, 3(1), 115–122.
- Rahman, W., Azizah, J., Asir, M., & Wijayanto, G. (2024). Exploring Successful Social Media Marketing Strategies In Enhancing Brand Engagement With Consumers In The Digital Era Eksplorasi Strategi Pemasaran Media Sosial Yang Sukses Dalam Meningkatkan Interaksi Merek Dengan Konsumen Di Era Digital. *Management Studies and Entrepreneurship Journal*, 5(1), 355–363.
- Rana, S., Shafi, F., Rasheed, A., & Malik, M. I. (2024). Online environmental platforms service and green consumer behavior nexus: a multi-mediator study. *Future Business Journal*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-023-00283-4>
- Rochdiani, D. (2023). Preferensi dan Kupuasan Pembelian Konsumen Terhadap Beras Berdasarkan Atributnya (Kasus Kabupaten Karawang Provinsi Jawa BArat). *Prospek Agribisnis*, 45363(1), 64–81.
- Rohmah, A. (2020). Pandemi Covid-19 dan Dampaknya terhadap Perilaku Konsumen di Indonesia. *Jurnal Inovasi Penelitian*, 1(7), 1373–1378. <https://doi.org/10.47492/jip.v1i7.247>
- Safira, J. A., & Aryansyah, A. F. (2023). Pengaruh Media Sosial dan Komunitas Online Terhadap Loyalitas Konsumen Produk Skintific: Peran Mediasi Keterlibatan Konsumen dan Hubungan Pengguna Merek. *Jimkes: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Kesatuan*, 11(3), 905–918.
- Safitri, L. S., Romalasari, A., & Suciati, F. (2022). Sikap Konsumen dalam Pembelian Online Produk Segar Sebelum dan Selama Pandemi Covid-19. *Buletin Poltanesa*, 23(1), 67–72. <https://doi.org/10.51967/tanesa.v23i1.1172>
- Sahira, D. A., & Fauziyah, E. (2021). Hubungan Persepsi Risiko Dengan Keputusan Pembelian Online Makanan Instan Pada Masa Pandemi Covid 19. *Agriscience*, 2(1), 32–47. <https://doi.org/10.21107/agriscience.v2i1.11244>

Saputri M, Titing, & Kurniadi. (2023). Pengaruh Kepercayaan Merek dan Keterlibatan Konsumen Terhadap Loyalitas Merek Pada Produk Ms Glow. *GLORY (Global Leadership Organizational Research in Management)*, 1(4), 325–339.

Sitaniapessy, A., Aunalal, Z. I., & Sitaniapessy, H. A. P. (2022). Pengaruh Kepercayaan, Kecintaan dan Keterikatan Emosional pada Loyalitas Merek. *Journal of Business Application*, 1(2), 305–306.

stefany, evy maya. (2016). Model Pembelajaran Somatis, Auditori, Visual Dan Intelektual (SAVI): Implementasi Pada Mata Pelajaran Teknologi Informasi Dan Komunikasi (TIK) Di SMP. *Eduatic - Scientific Journal of Informatics Education*, 1(2), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.21107/EDUTIC.V1I2.1542>